

User Handbook

2019

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Table of contents

Table of contents.....	2
1 Introduction	3
2 The RISIS-KNOWMAK conceptual framework.....	4
2.1 The basic focus: Knowledge in the 'Making' in KET and SGC	4
2.2 What does RISIS-KNOWMAK cover?	5
2.3 The RISIS-KNOWMAK data nexus.....	8
3 The RISIS-KNOWMAK indicators	10
3.1 Indicators on different modes of knowledge production	11
3.2 Different versions of indicators.....	13
4 Some guidance through the RISIS-KNOWMAK tool.....	15
4.1 The basic structure	15
4.2 The selection mechanisms	17
4.3 The analytical possibilities	18
4.4 Help and download menu	23
5 Glossary for users	24

1 Introduction

The focus of the **RISIS-KNOWMAK** (Knowledge in the 'making') tool is on the visualisation and investigation of the production of knowledge in the European Research Area, with a particular focus on knowledge related to Societal Grand Challenges (*SGC*¹) and Key Enabling Technologies (*KET*²). The tool is based on three existing data sources, i.e. **scientific publications** derived from the Web of Science database (CWTS-WoS database), **patents** derived from PATSTAT (UPEM-PATSTAT database) and **European R&D projects** derived from CORDIS (AIT-EUPRO database). Additionally, it features two newly developed, additional datasets, one concerned with **social innovation** projects and actors, the other with **user attention** as observed through social media. The main essence of RISIS-KNOWMAK is to provide a radically improved information basis for producing indicators on SGC and KET knowledge production activities (hot spots) and interactions (networks) in Europe. Indicators – derived from data collected on the organisational level – are geographically observed at the level of relevant subnational spatial units (metropolitan areas), and topically for about 400 KET and SGC topics.

This user handbook provides a **user-oriented guide** through the tool. It introduces in a compact manner the overall approach and framework of RISIS-KNOWMAK, and provides a comprehensive overview on all indicators available in the tool, and how they can be mobilized for analysing knowledge production activities across different geographical areas, topics and time periods. Moreover, it provides a usage guide of the tool, describing the dashboard and the main menus to be used for data visualisation, analysis and extraction.

The user handbook is organised as follows:

- *Section 2* provides a compact overview on the **conceptual framework and the overall approach of RISIS-KNOWMAK**, introducing the three integrative data dimensions, *geography, actors* and *topics*, and how source data are transformed and imputed to the tool along these integrative dimensions in form of user-friendly and applicable indicators in manifold contexts.
- *Section 3* introduces the **RISIS-KNOWMAK indicators** that are available in the tool for users. It will not only provide basic definitions, but also point to different possibilities for handling these indicators, such as normalisations or combinations.
- *Section 4* provides an illustrative **guidance through the RISIS-KNOWMAK tool**. It is intended to support the users in their navigation on the dashboard by means of screenshot, highlighting the main selection mechanisms, analytical possibilities, and data extraction mechanisms.
- *Section 5* details out some **warnings and Limitations** concerning the indicators to be taken into account by users for certain use cases. Such limitations and warnings relate to missing data, timing of indicators, etc.
- *Section 6* finally provides a compact **glossary of main terms** as service for the user to easily look up certain terms of central relevance and repeated occurrence.

Note that technical and methodological details are not set out in this user handbook, but can be accessed via the RISIS-KNOWMAK website (knowmak.eu) that provides the respective reports for the interested reader.

¹ <https://ec.europa.eu/programmes/horizon2020/en/h2020-section/societal-challenges>

² <https://ec.europa.eu/programmes/horizon2020/en/area/key-enabling-technologies>

2 The RISIS-KNOWMAK conceptual framework

2.1 The basic focus: Knowledge in the 'Making' in KET and SGC

Today it is widely recognised that new knowledge is one of the main determinants for successful innovation, and thus, crucial for the competitiveness of firms and the socio-economic development of regions and countries. Against this background, indicators on knowledge creation have gained increasing interest from different stakeholders, ranging from researchers across different disciplines, to research managers of companies, managers of research funding organisations and policy makers at different levels. However, most indicators on knowledge production, and accordingly the tools that present them, are derived at a quite aggregated level, both geographically (most often countries), and in particular thematically, not accounting for the topical diversity and dynamics of knowledge creation. Moreover, knowledge production is increasingly based on open interaction – recently referred to as co-creation – between different types of stakeholders, also most often neglected by existing tools.

By shifting attention to *Knowledge in the 'making'*, The RISIS-KNOWMAK tool exactly addresses these gaps, moving beyond static indicators by putting special emphasis on the dynamics of knowledge production, with indicators derived from organisational research activities, across relevant geographical areas, and more appropriate thematic classification schemes by means of dynamic and user-oriented ontologies. At the same, RISIS-KNOWMAK has a strong focus on making these new indicators available in a robust, illustrative and most effective way for different types of users within a user-friendly online working space, the RISIS-KNOWMAK tool (knowmak.eu).

Figure 1 RISIS-KNOWMAK conceptual framework

The RISIS-KNOWMAK focus on indicators on knowledge in the 'making', and its conveyance to different stakeholders by the RISIS-KNOWMAK tool in form of effective visualisations and a set of analytic possibilities is operationalised by the RISIS-KNOWMAK conceptual framework illustrated by Fig. 1. When we speak about knowledge in the 'making', we distinguish two forms, classical and non-classical knowledge production. By classical knowledge production we refer to knowledge codified in mostly classical data sources used to trace knowledge production, such as scientific **publications, patents** and (collaborative) **R&D projects**. However, next to these classical forms of knowledge production, RISIS-KNOWMAK accounts for new forms knowledge production that came into discussion more recently, and that are usually not recorded in classical data sources. Here, RISIS-KNOWMAK extends its focus, on the one hand, to knowledge production related to **social innovation** account for the increasing engagement of social actors in knowledge production processes, particularly relevant for the societal embedding of new knowledge. On the other hand, RISIS-KNOWMAK provides a glimpse on what we call **user attention**, i.e. attention of knowledge users in different places to specific topics recorded in social media in order to understand how different users mobilize new knowledge in manifold contexts.

Systematic information on these different types of knowledge production (see Section 2.3 and related RISIS-KNOWMAK documents for detailed information on the data sources) is prepared, transformed and transferred (see related documents on data preparation and transfer) to the RISIS-KNOWMAK central database. The latter stores all data necessary for indicators in the most efficient way (see related documents on the database and its characteristics). It integrates the data according to the three RISIS-KNOWMAK integrative dimensions, **geography, topics** and **actors**, and extends them with supporting data (e.g. population) necessary for indicators production (e.g. for normalisation issues). The integrative dimensions are essential for producing reliable and comparable indicators derived from different data sources, i.e. all data items are assigned to the same sets of spatial units, topical classes, and harmonized to sets of standardised key actors. The database comprises a separate indicators layers calculating all indicators to be conveyed to the RISIS-KNOWMAK tool for the user. The indicators are related to each type of knowledge production under consideration, but also to combinations of them (see Section 2.3).

Finally, the RISIS-KNOWMAK tool is most importantly from a user perspective as it constitutes the interface to the RISIS-KNOWMAK indicators and the users of the tool. The main premise of the tool is to keep its usage simple and reproducible, and providing a few but very effective analytic possibilities. In essence, the RISIS-KNOWMAK tool allows the user for three main analytical possibilities:

- **Exploration:** Allows the user to explore RISIS-KNOWMAK indicators directly in the tool, both in form of tables, but most importantly with different visualisation forms, such as geographical maps, bar charts and line diagrams.
- **Retrieval:** Allows the user to download selected indicators in a suitable format for further statistical analysis or combination with other data provided by the user or from other data sources.
- **Explanation:** Supports the user in the navigation through the tool with different online help features, and this user handbook, as well as some exemplary analysis that can be performed, and some data stories as illustrative examples.

Details on these analytical possibilities and how they are implemented in the tool are provided in Section 4.

2.2 What does RISIS-KNOWMAK cover?

Fig. 2 provides a snapshot on the RISIS-KNOWMAK coverage in terms of geography, topics and time lines. The European coverage of all RISIS-KNOWMAK indicators is given by a breakdown in 33 countries (including EU-28, EFTA and Associated countries), and below countries by 552 sub-national regions. The thematic perimeter is defined by the

Key Emerging Technologies (KETs) and Societal Grand Challenges (SGCs) as defined by the European Commission; as what concerns the time dimension, indicators are calculated (with the exception of a few cases) annually for the years 2000-2016.

Figure 2 RISIS-KNOWMAK coverage

The geographical areas covered by RISIS-KNOWMAK are illustrated by Fig. 3, comprising the 33 countries and the 552 regions, with the metropolitan regions highlighted in blue colour, and the adapted NUTS regions part of the study area in white. Note that all details on geographical breakdowns (mainly based on Eurostat) are given in related RISIS-KNOWMAK technical documents.

With the thematic perimeter delimited Key Enabling Technologies (KETs) and Societal Grand Challenges (SGCs), RISIS-KNOWMAK is not meant to cover all topical dimensions of knowledge production in Europe, but will focus on two types of topics, which have been identified as highly relevant for the construction of the European Research Area. Key enabling technologies (KET) have been defined by the European Commission as 'knowledge intensive and associated with high R&D intensity, rapid innovation cycles, high capital expenditures and highly skilled employment. Based on current research, economic analyses of market trends and their contribution to solving societal challenges, six KETs have been identified:

- **Nanotechnology**
- **Micro- and nano-electronics including semiconductors**
- **Advanced materials**
- **(industrial) Biotechnology**
- **Photonics**
- **Advanced manufacturing technologies**

The Societal Grand Challenges (SGCs) are the major challenges European society will face in the next several years, as identified by the Europe 2020 strategy. They also

represent a major pillar of the Horizon2020 EU Programme, i.e. the successor of FP7. The seven SGCs are:

- **Food security, sustainable agriculture, marine and maritime research, and the bio-economy**
- **Secure, clean and efficient energy**
- **Smart, green and integrated transport**
- **Climate action, resource efficiency and raw materials**
- **Health, demographic change and wellbeing**
- **Secure societies - protecting freedom and security of Europe and its citizens**
- **Europe in a changing world - inclusive, innovative and reflective societies**

As indicated by Fig. 2 the ontologies developed in RISIS-KNOWMAK disaggregate the first layer KETs and SGCs into a set of 135 subtopics, allowing the user to browse and extract indicators for detailed KET or SGC thematic areas (see also Section 4). Further details on the ontology and the topics available are given in respective technical document, and directly in the RISIS-KNOWMAK tool.

In order to be able to track changes over time, RISIS-KNOWMAK will provide indicators from the year 2000 to the most recent year available in the source datasets (currently 2015 or 2016). It is however possible that some of the older data are missing.

Figure 3 RISIS-KNOWMAK geographical coverage comprising metropolitan areas (blue) and adapted NUTS regions (Note: no metropolitan areas provided for Turkey by Eurostat)

2.3 The RISIS-KNOWMAK data nexus

As described in Section 2.1, the RISIS-KNOWMAK data nexus is composed of five original source datasets, three of them providing systematic information on classical knowledge production, two of them on non-classical knowledge production. The RISIS-KNOWMAK data nexus with its fixe source data is given by Box 1.

Box. 1 RISIS-KNOWMAK data nexus

	<p>CWTS-WoS Enhanced version of Thomson Reuters publication and citation indexes, covering almost 13,000 current international peer reviewed journals and around 15 million publications, all their references and information on social media attention in publications</p>
	<p>IFRIS-PATSTAT Global patent data recorded in PATSTAT (patent holders, inventors, technological classification, fine grain patents type selection, etc.), enriched by external data sources and cleaned/standardized information.</p>
	<p>EUPRO Systematic information on R&D projects and all participating organizations funded by the European Framework Programmes (EU-FPs). EUPRO covers information on projects and participations (FP1-H2020)</p>
	<p>ESID Database on social innovation, employing advanced text mining techniques to identify and characterize social innovation projects and actors from known databases and additional sources from the web</p>

For the interested reader and user of the RISIS-KNOWMAK tool, we briefly describe each of the source datasets, most of them also available via the data infrastructure RISIS³:

CWTS-WoS database on Scientific publications: CWTS-WoS is an enhanced version of the Thomson Reuters publication and citation indexes, developed by the University of Leiden. It covers tens of thousands of current international peer-reviewed journals and over 18 million publications including all their references. The data system is enhanced with links at the level of individual publications to other major databases, such as PATSTAT (patent analysis) and Altmetrics (social media, blogs, mainstream news media, readership, etc.). An important characteristic of the CWTS Citation Index system is the combination of smart algorithms and expert manual data cleaning, which provides a high quality unification of names and addresses. Moreover, the database enables accurate citation counts by linking both citing and cited publications. CWTS has also developed a publication-level based classification (around 4000 research areas), providing a dynamic structure of science, independent of journals. This represents more accurately the current practices in research, being more interdisciplinary.

³ <https://risis.eu/>.

The IFRIS-PATSTAT database on Patents: IFRIS-PATSTAT consists of global patent data recorded in PATSTAT and contains information about patents, patent holders, inventors, technological classification, links with previous patents and so on. The PATSTAT data has been enriched by external data sources and cleaned/standardized information. PATSTAT is provided by the European Patent Office (EPO) and gathers the information of all patent offices in the world, enabling a unique worldwide coverage of all patenting activities [2]. The IFRIS-PATSTAT also addresses some of the pitfalls identified, such as the weakness in inventor addresses for foreign patents in the United States Patent and Trademark Office (USPTO), in the coverage of EPO for patenting in Europe, and in the standardisation of names of patent holders.

The EUPRO database on European projects: EUPRO has been developed by the Austrian Institute of Technology and comprises systematic information on R&D projects and all participating organisations funded by the European Framework Programmes. It covers information on: projects (such as project objectives and achievements, project costs, total funding, start and end date, contract type, information on the call) and details of participating organisations. It includes project title, summaries and keywords, which enables the application of RISIS-KNOWMAK ontologies to the database. Substantial effort has been made to improve the quality and the level of standardisation of the data by methods such as identification of unique organisation names and types, regionalisation (i.e. assignment of locations to European NUTS regions), as well as regular integration of new data and links with other databases.

The European Social Innovation Database (ESID): ESID is the most comprehensive database on social innovation, employing advanced text mining techniques to identify and characterize social innovation projects and actors from known databases and additional sources from the web. As it is based on semi-automatic and automatic information retrieval and knowledge discovery techniques, it is much more sustainable than the existing databases that rely on continued human coding. ESID is able to be updated with minimal human supervision. The more data it includes, the more precise its data collection will be and the less human supervision it will require thanks to machine learning.

3 The RISIS-KNOWMAK indicators

The RISIS-KNOWMAK tool is intended to provide users with already pre-computed and relevant indicators on knowledge creation activities, and to present these indicators in effective and illustrative ways. Therefore, the different users interested in different aspects of knowledge, e.g. in terms of topics addressed, hot spots of knowledge creation, co-creation patterns in specific topics in Europe, etc., are expected to directly enter into concrete, and real-world analytical questions (user scenarios) with the indicators provided by the RISIS-KNOWMAK tool.

In this sense, the RISIS-KNOWMAK indicators are meant to provide

- relevant **synthetic information** to users in a condensed form,
- conveyed to the user with **effective and illustrative visualisations** via an easy-to-use user interface.

At the same all indicator values are available for download in the RISIS-KNOWMAK for purposes of further analysis of different kinds.

Figure 4 The RISIS-KNOWMAK indicators systems

Fig. 4 provides an overview on the RISIS-KNOWMAK indicators system. In relation to the RISIS-KNOWMAK conceptual framework (see Fig. 1), we distinguish between indicators on classical knowledge production, and indicators on non-classical knowledge production. Classical knowledge production comprises three types of knowledge, namely scientific knowledge (captured in form of scientific publications), technological knowledge (captured in form of patenting activities) and project-based knowledge (captured by formalised joint R&D projects). Indicators on non-classical knowledge production involve social innovation (as captured by social innovation projects), and Citizens' attention (as captured by the identification of influential users in social media). Box 2 lists all basic indicators available via the RISIS-KNOWMAK tool (so called entity-level indicators, i.e. indicators that refer to an individual combination of actors, topics

and space). They are explained in further detail in terms of measurement and interpretation in the specific subsections below.

Box. 2 Overview of main indicators across different modes of knowledge production (Note: will be constantly enhanced during the whole project)

Category	Indicator
	Number of publications Number of publications in the Top10% cited Number of intercontinental scientific collaborations` Number of Open Access publications Number of tweeted publications (user attention)
	Number of patent applications Number of transnational patent applications
	Number of EU-FP participations Number of EU-FP coordination
	Lists of social innovation projects per spatial entity and topic, with information on project title, website and actors (available via factsheets, see Section 4.3)

3.1 Indicators on different modes of knowledge production

In order to support the user in the interpretation of the different indicators provided by the RISIS-KNOWMAK tool, we explain each indicator in the following.

The indicators listed here can be derived for any combination of selective dimensions (country/regions, topics, time) (see also Section 4).

The indicators listed here can usually be derived as raw counts, or normalized (e.g. by population) (see Section 3.3).

The RISIS-KNOWMAK tool also provides combinations of these indicators, e.g. a composite knowledge intensity indicator (see Section 3.2)

Scientific knowledge production**Number of publications**

The count of publications for a given combination of dimensions from the Thomson Reuters' Web of Science database (Science Citation Index Expanded, Social Sciences Citation Index, and Arts & Humanities Citation Index). Only publications of the Web of Science document types *article* and *review* are considered.

Number of publications in the top10% cited

The number of publications in the top10% cited from the Thomson Reuters' Web of Science database (Science Citation Index Expanded, Social Sciences Citation Index, and Arts & Humanities Citation Index). Only publications of the Web of Science document types *article* and *review* are considered

Number of international scientific collaborations

Number of publications with collaboration of institutions from more than one country

Number of Open Access (OA) publications

Number of publication that are published in OA journals or other OA in Web of Science

Number of tweeted publications

Number of publications that have been tweeted on the Social Media Platform Twitter (at least one time)

Technological knowledge production**Number of patent applications**

The count of priority patent applications based on the inventors locations in full counting (priority refers to the first application date and area).

Number of transnational patent applications

Number of patents applied for in more than one country.

Projects-based knowledge production

Number of EU-FP participations

The count of participations to EU-FP projects based on the locations of participants to a project (full counting).

Number of EU-FP coordinations

The count of coordinations to EU-FP projects, based on the location of the coordinator to a project.

3.2 Different versions of indicators

The indicators listed in Section 3.1 can be derived in different forms as described in compact form in what follows:

Raw values

Raw counts of knowledge production outputs for a given aggregation level (for example counts of publications, projects, patents).

Normalised indicators

In order to account for size differences between the spatial entities a user is focusing on, indicators can also be derived in normalized, simply by expressing the raw values relative to a specific size measure. Currently, one normalisation approach is available in RISIS-KNOWMAK:

Population

Total number of people (inhabitants, i.e. resident populations) in that area at a given time

Special and combined indicators

The RISIS-KNOWMAK tool provides a number of combinations of the indicators available for different kinds of useful analytical purposes. Those combinations refer to composite indicators (i.e. the synthetic combination of a set of indicators), but also to specific transformations to indicate e.g. specialisations or relations between indicators (e.g. publications per patents). Currently, the following combined indicators are available:

- **Knowledge production share:** Average of the shares of projects, publications and patents; gives an overall impression of knowledge production activities, in particular when comparing a larger set of regions/countries or whole Europe
- **Knowledge production intensity:** Total production share normalised by population

- **Science share intensity:** Total scientific knowledge production share normalised by population
- **Technology share intensity:** Total technological knowledge production share normalised by population

Network-based indicators

The importance of collaborative research has been widely discussed in the literature but also by policy in the recent. Therefore, RISIS-KNOWMAK integrates indicators on the positioning of regions / countries in R&D collaboration networks in form of so-called network centralities. They are, as the combined indicators, available for the geographical entry point, not for the topical one. For each knowledge production type under consideration, one network centrality measure is made available and defined as follows:

	<p>Publication degree centrality Regional/Country degree centrality in publication networks (number of cross-regional / cross-country co-publications by topic)</p>
	<p>Patent degree centrality Regional/Country degree centrality in patent networks (number of cross-regional / cross-country co-inventions by topic)</p>
	<p>Project degree centrality Regional/Country degree centrality in project networks (number of cross-regional / cross-country FP participations by topic)</p>

Regional / Country factsheets

The **regional / country factsheet** is one of the core services for users of the RISIS-KNOWMAK tool. It simply provides ad-hoc basic information for each spatial entity, when scrolling over it on the map, or in a separate area of the dashboard when a spatial entity is selected (see Section 4). The factsheets list for the most recent year available:

- Population
- GDP
- Number of publications
- Number of patents
- Number of projects

Actors

RISIS-KNOWMAK provides information on the top actors (Top-5 public organisations and Top-5 private companies) active in knowledge production (projects, publications, patents) in a specific topic and spatial entity (region or country). This is based on harmonized actor information between the three conventional source datasets. The actors are listed (with some additional information) in the factsheets when clicking on a spatial entity (country or region) (see Section 4.3).

4 Some guidance through the RISIS-KNOWMAK tool

4.1 The basic structure

The RISIS-KNOWMAK tool allows the user for three main analytical possibilities:

- **Exploration:** Allows the user to explore RISIS-KNOWMAK indicators directly in the tool, both in form of tables, but most importantly with different visualisation forms, such as geographical maps, bar charts and line diagrams.
- **Retrieval:** Allows the user to download selected indicators in a suitable format for further statistical analysis or combination with other data provided by the user or from other data sources.
- **Explanation:** Supports the user in the navigation through the tool with different online help features, and this user handbook, as well as some exemplary analysis that can be performed, and some data stories as illustrative examples.

Figure 5 provides the main dashboard view for **data exploration and retrieval in the RISIS-KNOWMAK tool**. The basic steps to display or retrieve data are

1.

The **explore menu** for **(A)** selecting the indicator; **(B)** normalisation (not normalized or normalized by population); **(C)** dimension (location or topics) and **(D)** time to be displayed. These four choices are mandatory.

2.

The optional **filter menu** for further filtering data in terms of **(A)** geographical and **(B)** topical coverage according to user's needs.

3.

The **show menu** for **analytical choices** to investigate selected data with the different **(A)** **(B)** **(C)** visualization (exploration mode) or **(C)** export data (retrieval mode)

4.

The help and download menu featuring one functionality to access the handbook, and guided tour, and a functionality for downloading selected indicators

Figure 5 Main dashboard view

4.2 The selection mechanisms

The selection mechanism includes **two main steps**:

1

Selection of an **indicator**, and specify the exploration mode ("*explore by*") in terms of **geography** and/or **topics** and *in time*.

The selection of the indicators to be displayed requires three choices by the user:

A. Selecting the indicator to be explored.

A

- a. Scientific knowledge production
 - i. **Number of publications**
 - ii. **Number of publications in the top10% cited**
 - iii. **Number of international scientific collaborations**
- b. Technological knowledge production
 - i. **Number of patent applications**
 - ii. **Number of international patent collaborations**
- c. Project-based knowledge production
 - i. **Number of EU-FP participations**
 - ii. **Number of EU-FP coordinations**
- d. Composite
 - i. **Total production intensity**
 - ii. **Total production share**
- e. Normalisation
 - i. **Number of inhabitants**

B. Explore selected indicator by
Geography

B

- a. **Country**
- b. **Region**

OR

Topics

- c. **Class**: 6 First layer KET and 7 SGC
- d. **Subclass**: 135 thematic subareas of KETs and SGCs

C. In year

- a. **Years** 2010 – 2016,
- b. default year 2014 (no patents for 15/16)

C

2

Filtering the pre-selection from **1.**

The selected indicator can be filtered by

A. Countries and regions

A

B. Classes and subclasses

B

By default, all countries and topics are selected. Ticking the all countries/all regions and the all topics/all subtopics box selects/de-selects all entities. Specific countries/regions and classes/subclasses can be selected by ticking single boxes.

4.3 The analytical possibilities

The analytical possibilities available by September 2018 are the **Map View**, **Bar Chart** and **Table View** (incl. data download). Additional ones will be added constantly e.g. line diagrams for illustrating the time dimension or scatter plots for relating indicators to each other.

3

Before the three views are explained below, attention is shifted to the **Show** option valid for all three views:

The Show option is needed to specify in the three analytical views the class or subclass to be displayed in case more than one classes/subclasses have been selected in the filtering part. If all classes/subclasses should be shown, "**each selected**" must be hit (is also the default option). Note that in the map view, "**each selected**" is not feasible, as only one class/subclass can be shown in one map.

A. Map view

The map view allows the user to illustrate the spatial distribution of indicator values across Europe, choosing countries or regions as units of observation. Indicator values are classified statistically into five classes (natural breaks), with yellow to red colours from low to high values.

It contains the following elements/functions (see **orange boxes** in the screenshot below):

- a. Legend: contains the colours and the range for the five classes produced for the indicator values
- b. **Zoom** into map by using + and – button or mouse wheel
- c. **Display country/regional factsheet** on right side of dashboard by
- d. scrolling or clicking on a country/region
- e. To **display value** mouse over country/region
- f. **Download csv (data retrieval in .csv format)**

Figure 6 Map view

Regional / Country factsheets

Clicking on a spatial entity, i.e. region or country, opens the region or country factsheet right-hand. It gives information on three relevant dimension for the spatial entity under consideration that can be reached by clicking on the respective tabs:

- a. General:** Provides information on population and knowledge creation intensity for the the three main knowledge creation types (patents, projects, publications)
- b. Actors:** provides information on the top actors (Top-5 public organisations and Top-5 private companies) active in knowledge production (projects, publications, patents) in a specific topic and spatial entity (region or country). This is based on harmonized actor information between the three conventional source datasets. The actors are listed (with some additional information) in the factsheets when clicking on a spatial entity (country or region)
- c. Social Innovation Projects:** Lists the social innovation projects of the spatial entity and topic, with information on project title, website and actors

B. Bar Chart

The bar chart view displays the selected indicators by means of a classical bar chart, with each bar representing an indicator value for a country/region and/or class/subclass.

It contains the following elements/functions (see **orange boxes** in the screenshot below):

- a. **Legend** contains the year displayed (hidden behind country factsheet)
- b. **Zoom** into the bar chart by narrowing down and/or moving the grey area of the small chart on the bottom of the page
- c. **Display regional / country factsheets** on right side of dashboard by
- d. Scrolling or clicking on a country/region
- e. To **display value** mouse over bar
- f. **Sort** the data in ascending/descending alphabetical order (A-Z/Z-A), or by increasing/decreasing numerical values (0-9/9-0)
- g. **Download csv (data retrieval in .csv format)**

Figure 7 Bar Chart view

C. Table view

The table view has the function to display raw values of the selected indicator in table format.

- b.** Select rows per page (default = 10)
- c.** **Display regional / country factsheets** on right side of dashboard by
- d.** Scrolling or clicking on a country/region
- e.** Sort function (for each column left hand to the columns header)
- f.** **Download csv (data retrieval in .csv format)**
- g.** **Go to next page**

Figure 8 Table view

The screenshot illustrates the 'Table view' in the KNOWMAK application. Key elements include:

- Navigation Bar (1):** Shows 'Explore', 'NUMBER OF PATENT APPLICATIONS', 'NOT NORMALISED', and 'grouped by'.
- Filter Sidebar (2):** Contains 'Filter by' with 'Countries and Regions' (A) and 'Classes and Subclasses' (B).
- Main Table (3):** Displays data for 'INDUSTRIAL BIOTECHNOLOGY' in 2012. Columns include Region, Year, Topic, and Number of patent applications. A sort icon (e) is visible on the 'Topic' header.
- Factsheet (4):** A sidebar on the right shows details for 'Eindhoven, Netherlands', including 'Year: 2012 Class: industrial biotechnology' and various metrics like 'Publications (Rank 124)', 'Patents (Rank 6)', 'Projects (Rank 96)', 'Public Organisations', 'Private Companies', and 'Social Innovation Projects'.
- Footer (b, g):** Shows 'Rows per page: 10' and '1-10 of 553'.

4.4 Help and download menu

The help and download includes the following options

- A. Go to start page
- B. Download dialogue. While selected data can be downloaded directly in each view in .csv format, the download dialogue enable user to download data for multiple years and indicators and is therefore in particular useful for advanced data retrieval.
- C. Introductory tour including step-by-step guidance through the RISIS-KNOWMAK tool
- D. Help including download option of this user handbook.

Figure 9 Help and download menu

5 Glossary for users

Links within this handbook are underlined, external links underlined and italic

- **Actor** (see also Standardized actors) in RISIS-KNOWMAK are aggregated entities, mostly organizations like universities and firms, as they are identified in RISIS-KNOWMAK data sources. As such, they are already subject to some level of standardization (for example in respect to name variants), but they are not fully standardized, specifically across datasets.
- **Class:** The six **first layer KETs** (Nanotechnology; Micro- and nano-electronics including semiconductors; Advanced materials; (industrial) Biotechnology; Photonics; Advanced manufacturing technologies) and **seven first layer SGCs** (Food security, sustainable agriculture, marine and maritime research, and the bio-economy; Secure, clean and efficient energy; Smart, green and integrated transport; Climate action, resource efficiency and raw materials; Health, demographic change and wellbeing; Secure societies - protecting freedom and security of Europe and its citizens; Europe in a changing world - inclusive, innovative and reflective societies.
- **CORDIS:** Community Research and Development Information Service (EC's public data repository and information portal)
- **Country:** Referring to the national units of analysis, covering the EU, candidate and associate countries (see RISIS-KNOWMAK coverage, Section 2.2).
- **CWTS-WoS database:** An enhanced version of the Thomson Reuters publication and citation indexes, developed by the University of Leiden. It covers tens of thousands of current international peer-reviewed journals and over 18 million publications including all their references. The data system is enhanced with links at the level of individual publications to other major databases, such as PATSTAT (patent analysis) and Altmetrics (social media, blogs, mainstream news media, readership, etc.). An important characteristic of the CWTS Citation Index system is the combination of smart algorithms and expert manual data cleaning, which provides a high quality unification of names and addresses. Moreover, the database enables accurate citation counts by linking both citing and cited publications. CWTS has also developed a publication-level based classification (around 4000 research areas), providing a dynamic structure of science, independent of journals. This represents more accurately the current practices in research, being more interdisciplinary.
- **DG:** Directorate-general (top tier entity of EC organisational structure; responsible for a policy area)
- **EC:** European Commission
- **ERA:** European Research Area
- **ESID:** European Social Innovation Database comprising novel and systematic information on social innovation projects (see Section 3).
- **EU:** European Union
- **EUPRO** (see also European projects): FP projects and participants database constructed and maintained by AIT Austrian Institute of Technology.
- **European projects:** EUPRO has been developed by AIT Austrian Institute of Technology and comprises systematic information on R&D projects and all participating organisations funded by the European Framework Programmes. It covers information on: projects (such as project objectives and achievements, project costs, total funding, start and end date, contract type, information on the call) and details of participating organisations. It includes project title, summaries and keywords, which enables the application of RISIS-KNOWMAK ontologies to the database. Substantial effort has been made to improve the quality and the level of standardisation of the data by methods such as identification of unique organisation names and types, regionalisation (i.e. assignment of locations to European NUTS regions), as well as regular integration of new data and links with other databases.

- **FirmReg:** RISIS firms register used in combination with the register of public-sector organizations (OrgReg) for the identification of Standardized actors . The perimeter includes all firms covered by the three RISIS database Corporate Innovation Board (CIB), VICO and Cheetah Database (Database on Fast Growing Medium Sized Firms). The FirmReg firms are either individual firms or the group-level entity – Global Ultimate Owner (GUO) or Industrial Global Ultimate Owner (GUOI), when the GUO is not an industrial company.
- **Firms:** see FirmReg
- **FP** (see also European projects): European Framework Programmes for Research and Innovation
- **FUA:** Functional Urban Area. The functional urban area consists of a city plus its commuting zone. This is defined in the EU-OECD functional urban area definition (EU-OECD FUA).
- **GDP:** Gross Domestic Product, used for normalisation of indicators. As an aggregate measure of production, GDP is equal to the sum of the gross value added of all resident institutional units engaged in production, plus any taxes on products and minus any subsidies on products. Gross value added is the difference between output and intermediate consumption.
- **IFRIS-PATSTAT database:** A database that consists of global Patents data recorded in PATSTAT and contains information about patents, patent holders, inventors, technological classification, links with previous patents and so on. The PATSTAT data has been enriched by external data sources and cleaned/standardized information. PATSTAT is provided by the European Patent Office (EPO) and gathers the information of all patent offices in the world, enabling a unique worldwide coverage of all patenting activities. The IFRIS-PATSTAT also addresses some of the pitfalls identified, such as the weakness in inventor addresses for foreign patents in the United States Patent and Trademark Office (USPTO), in the coverage of EPO for patenting in Europe, and in the standardisation of names of patent holders.
- **Indicators** (see also Normalisation and Chapter 3) are quantitative variables, which are meant to provide some information or proxy on a characteristics of reality ((Barré 2001); (Lepori and Reale 2012)). For example, the number of publication for a university or a region is meant to provide a measure of the volume of the scholarly output. As detailed further in chapter 3 of this handbook, RISIS-KNOWMAK will include two basic types of indicators, i.e. activity and linkages indicators. Indicators can be constructed in different forms, including raw counts of variables aggregated by some dimension, normalized indicators (by other variables and by distribution), as well as more complex indicators like specialisation indexes. The RISIS-KNOWMAK tool is an indicator tool: users will not be able in principle to access micro-level data, for example individual publications, but will be provided different types of indicators relative to combinations of the integrative elements. Indicators are meant to provide synthetic information to users in a condensed form, therefore avoiding too complex visualization or large amount of data to be examined. Indicators need to be grounded on specific user questions and theoretical representation of the considered phenomena. On the other hand, indicators are also grounded on statistical analysis of the available data, which might highlight regularities and, for example, correlations between variables.
- **KET** (see also Class): Key Enabling Technologies. KETs are a group of six technologies: micro and nanoelectronics, nanotechnology, industrial biotechnology, advanced materials, photonics, and advanced manufacturing technologies. They have applications in multiple industries and help tackle societal challenges. Countries and regions that fully exploit KETs will be at the forefront of creating advanced and sustainable economies.
- **RISIS-KNOWMAK:** KNOWledge in the MAKing in European Society, the project's acronym

- **Normalisation:** All indicators in RISIS-KNOWMAK will be provided in their basic form as raw counts or scores (volume indicators), for example the number of publications or of patents for a specific geographical space or actor. In order to enhance comparability and make comparisons easier to users, counts will also be normalized in some different ways.
 - a) **Size-normalized indicators.** Against a variable for input or size: this applies for geographical spaces by using GDP or population. Normalization by input or size will in principle not be applied for actors, lacking a common definition of size.
 - b) **Ratio indicators** computed as a ratio or proportion between variables. For example, indicators of scientific collaboration can be normalized against the total number of publications, giving a proportion in the range [0,1], which is in principle more comparable. Ratio indicators are computed only if the denominator exceeds a certain threshold, otherwise they are left blank.
 - c) **Rank indicators.** Against the distribution of the same indicators for similar units, for example other regions. Such a normalization is particularly useful to benchmark a region or actor, whether for example it has a large volume of output than the average region.
- **NUTS** (see also region): The Classification of Territorial Units for Statistics (NUTS; French: Nomenclature des unités territoriales statistiques) is a geocode standard for referencing the subdivisions of countries for statistical purposes. The standard is developed and regulated by the European Union, and thus only covers the member states of the EU in detail. For each EU member country, a hierarchy of three NUTS levels is established by Eurostat in agreement with each member state; the subdivisions in some levels do not necessarily correspond to administrative divisions within the country. The current NUTS classification, valid from 1 January 2015, lists 98 regions at NUTS 1, 276 regions at NUTS 2 and 1342 regions at NUTS 3 level.
- **Ontology (see also topics and vocabularies):** Within RISIS-KNOWMAK, topics are handled through the development of ontologies, which will allow bridging the different languages used by users and within data sources for similar content. The purpose of the RISIS-KNOWMAK ontologies is to act as a bridge between the users and the underlying data, by on the one hand enabling the users to browse topics, see related topics, and widen their search (as described in Section 4.4). The ontology structure is built in three layers, the first one corresponding to KET and SGC. Unlike classifications, the ontology structure is hierarchical but nevertheless allows multiple inheritance (i.e. cross-linkages between branches). For example, “nanobiotechnology” is a Subclass of both “nanoscience and technology” and “biotechnologies”. Multiple inheritance is required because terms and concepts are not unique to single KETs and SGCs – there is much overlap in technology between these areas, which needs to be reflected in our system. The ontology will also be available as entry point to the tool for users. Users will have the option of a filtered search using the keywords of the ontology in order to identify topics of interest within the ontology and then access to indicators by class.
- **OrgReg:** RISIS register of public-sector organizations used in combination with the RISIS firms register (FirmReg) for the identification of Standardized actors. They include Higher Education Institutions, Public Research Organizations, Private-Non-Profit Research Organizations, Research Hospitals and Public Administration entities involved in research. The total number of entities involved is expected to be around 5,000, including however a large number of entities with no or very few research outputs. OrgReg provides for stable IDs for these organizations, as well as for tracking demographic changes over the time-period covered by RISIS-KNOWMAK, i.e. 2000-2015. OrgReg also provides some basic descriptive information including the organizational type, geographical location, foundation year and the whole demography from the year 2000 onwards. For Higher Education Institutions (HEIs) data on revenues, staff, students are available from the European Tertiary Education Register (ETER), but limited to the years 2008, 2011-2014. For other public entities, data availability is far more uncertain. The list of public-sector research organization

in RISIS-KNOWMAK will therefore be identical with OrgReg and synchronized in real-time with it.

- **Patents:** A form of intellectual property that gives its owner the right to exclude others from making, using, selling, and importing an invention for a limited period of time, usually twenty years.
- **Patent family:** A patent family is a set of patents taken in various countries to protect a single invention (when a first application in a country – the priority – is then extended to other offices).
- **PATSTAT** (see also [Patents](#)): Patent statistics database by the European Patent Office
- **Public-sector research organizations:** see OrgReg
- **Projects** (see also EUPRO and [European projects](#)): In RISIS-KNOWMAK projects denote formalised and publicly funded collaborative R&D projects (e.g. under the heading of the European Framework Programme).
- **Regions:** RISIS-KNOWMAK will aggregate data and indicators at the level of subnational regions, identified through an adapted classification from the EUROSTAT NUTS classification⁴ that includes the **EUROSTAT metropolitan regions** and the remaining regions identified at the NUTS level 2 (adapted).
- **RISIS** (see also [OrgReg](#) and [FirmReg](#)): *Research Infrastructure for Science and Innovation (policy) Studies*.
- **RTDI:** Research, Technological Development, and Innovation
- **Scientific publications:** In RISIS-KNOWMAK referring to publications in international peer-reviewed journals covered by WoS.
- **SGC** (see also topics): [Societal Grand Challenges](#)
- **Standardized actors** are those actors subject to process of standardization across the database and that are identified through stable identifiers set in the RISIS register of public-sector organizations ([OrgReg](#)), respectively the RISIS firms register ([FirmReg](#)). These actors are therefore identified uniquely across data sources.
- **Subclass:** 135 thematic subtopics below the first layer KET/SGC class level.
- **Topics:** Relates to a thematic view on the indicators, distinguishing between classes and [Subclasses](#). The topical perimeter of RISIS-KNOWMAK covers Key Emerging Technologies ([KET](#)) and Societal Grand Challenges ([SGC](#)) (see Section 2.2).
- **UI:** User interface
- **Vocabularies** (see also [ontology](#)): Topics within the ontology are associated with vocabularies, i.e. set of words, which are associated (usually to more than one) topic. In ontological terms, vocabularies are sets of instances, or terms, attached to classes, which represent the topic. For example, “tumour imaging” might be an instance of the class “nanotechnology in cancer”. Vocabularies have two key functions in RISIS-KNOWMAK: a) To link topics with data items, for example publications. Data items will be tagged with keywords and, through them, can therefore be associated to topics. b) To link topics with search queries by users (see below).
- **WoS:** Web of Science, citation database owned by Onex Corporation and Baring Private Equity Asia and maintained by Clarivate Analytics since 2017

⁴ <http://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/web/nuts/overview>.

